

QoE-Driven Spot Pricing Schemes For Edge User Allocation Across the Distributed Cloud-Edge Continuum

Michail Filippou¹, Prodromos Makris¹, Aristotelis Kretsis¹, Panagiotis Kokkinos¹, and Emmanouel Varvarigos¹

Institute of Communications and Computer Systems, School of Electrical and Computer Engineering,
National Technical University of Athens (NTUA) Athens, Greece
{m_filippou, prodromosmakris, akretsis, kokkinop, vmanos}@mail.ntua.gr

Abstract

In the distributed cloud-edge continuum (CEC), high unpredictability and variability of workloads is a major challenge for an edge service provider (ESP), who wants to achieve an optimal trade-off between the quality of experience (QoE) it offers to its heterogeneous edge users (EUs) and the cost for dynamically renting edge resources. In this paper, we propose QoE-aware spot pricing schemes that align edge users' incentives with ESP's system-level objectives. In particular, the proposed personalized spot pricing scheme (PSP) deals with the "tragedy of the commons" phenomenon by applying personalized discounts to elastic EUs according to each one's individual contribution to overall system's cost reduction. Simulation results show that PSP affects EUs' behavior much more efficiently than the state-of-the-art spot pricing scheme by: i) ensuring fair allocation of financial benefits among EUs so that inelastic users do not benefit from the actions of elastic users, ii) considerably reducing system's cost (from 15% in low elasticity up to 35% in high elasticity scenarios), and iii) negligibly deteriorating aggregated EUs' welfare up to 2.5%.

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation and Background

Distributed Cloud Edge Continuum (CEC) aims at supporting a plethora of novel applications at the network's edge (e.g. AR/VR, smart city apps, industrial IoT, interactive gaming, etc.) that require ultra-low latency, local big data processing, security, privacy, energy efficiency, etc. These applications, whose demand increases exponentially, should mostly rely on edge servers with limited capacity, while heterogeneous edge users may compete to achieve the maximum possible Quality of Experience (QoE) [1]. In such an ecosystem, high unpredictability and variability of workloads is a major challenge for the Edge User Allocation (EUA) problem. So far, vertical and/or horizontal scaling of edge resources is mostly used as a solution. Recently, demand-side management approaches (e.g. dynamic pricing, market-based frameworks, auction theory, game theory) have been proposed to achieve workload balancing by taking into account self-interested edge users' welfare maximization objective, too [2]. At the same time, innovative business models boost the importance of striking an optimal trade-off between the QoE that an Edge Service Provider (ESP) offers to its edge users and its profitability margins (i.e. by minimizing the cost of renting edge resources). ESP is a newly introduced actor that acts as a mediator between edge infrastructure owner (EIO) and edge users being responsible for dynamically monitoring, orchestrating, deploying, configuring and maintaining the computing resources used by the EUs [3] [4]. Indeed, cloud-native application development has become the holy grail of S/W engineering, enabling the breakdown of a monolithic application into smaller, loosely-coupled S/W components called microservices. These microservices may run

in several edge servers, facilitating enhancements in the application’s performance, flexibility, and resilience together with better resource utilization [5]. Thus, there is a need for advanced middleware tools (operated by an ESP or a 3rd party entity) that facilitate the seamless and secure CEC’s operation [6] according to the recently introduced hyper-distributed computing paradigm [7]. In this paper, we propose novel QoE-aware spot pricing schemes that align the EU’s incentives with system-level objectives that an ESP [6] or else a resource association/aggregator [7] wants to achieve.

1.2 Related Works

Several optimization methods have been proposed to address the EUA problem like our recent work [5]. These solutions usually require global system’s knowledge, and assume that EUs and ESPs are non-decision makers, while they are not easily scalable to many rational actors with conflicting interests. However, in the real world, ESPs and EUs are rational self-interested entities, exercising their partial or complete autonomy to achieve their objectives, while they are not willing to disclose their private utility functions [2]. Game-theoretical tools like [8] address most of the above-mentioned requirements, but they are not capable of enforcing any desired structures to the system. Therefore, several works on auction theory, market-based frameworks and pricing schemes for CEC have been recently proposed [1] [2]. In this paper, we consider a similar system model to [3], [4], [9], [10], [11]. In contrast to these works, we focus on modeling: i) elastic EUs, who are willing to receive monetary rewards at the expense of a lower QoE, ii) a demand-side management scheme in which price-anticipating edge users (instead of price-taking) compete with each other to maximize their welfare. The idea of elastic resource provisioning (on the supply side) and serving interruptible workloads is a common business practice of today’s largest cloud service providers (i.e. AmazonEC2, Google Cloud, Microsoft Azure). Their spot Virtual Machine (VM) pricing schemes offer much lower prices at the expense of offering preemptive VM instances. Nevertheless, all “winning” users are charged with the same spot price, under-exploiting thus the heterogeneous users’ elasticity (i.e., expressed as the number of VMs vs. QoE utility function per user) and payment potential as a function of time. In this paper, we propose a novel Personalized Spot Pricing (PSP) scheme that rewards EUs according to their contribution to system’s cost reduction (i.e. a more elastic EU gets a greater reward than a less elastic EU). We claim that this PSP feature is even more important in the hyper-distributed computing continuum and related business ecosystem, because proper incentivization of elastic EUs and competitive ESP business models in relatively small-scale edge computing infrastructures can be a key boost factor for further investments on distributed edge computing and novel cloud-native applications’ development.

1.3 Contributions

Our paper’s contributions can be summarized as follows:

- A Spot Pricing (SP) scheme is proposed that directly connects the supply-side costs of an ESP with the demand-side preferences of price-anticipating EUs. Furthermore, a PSP scheme is also proposed that applies personalized rewards to elastic EUs based on each one’s individual contribution to overall system’s cost reduction. The proposed system model follows a decentralized architecture, so that EUs do not need to reveal their utility functions and the system can achieve the scalability required by the hyper-distributed computing paradigm.

- We show that the PSP can achieve an attractive and easily configurable trade-off among three Key Performance Indicators (KPIs): i) aggregated EUs’ welfare (KPI 1), ii) system’s cost reduction (KPI 2), and iii) fair allocation of rewards (KPI 3). Hence, the proposed framework can be used as a simulation tool for a competitive ESP to exhaustively evaluate the performance of various pricing and EUA strategies via running many “what-if” scenarios before deciding to apply them in the real-world market.

2 System Model

We introduce a new business actor in the hyper-distributed cloud-edge continuum called Edge Service Provider (ESP). The ESP acts as an intermediary/broker entity between the edge infrastructure owner (EIO) and the edge users (EUs). ESP’s main responsibility is to dynamically monitor, orchestrate, deploy, configure and maintain the computing resources to be used by the EUs. We elaborate on the HORIZON-KDT-JU CLEVER [6] and HORIZON EU EMPYREAN project’s architecture [7], which consists of several layers, each corresponding to specific middleware tools that facilitate the hyper-distributed computing continuum’s secure and seamless operation. In this paper, we focus on the orchestration layer (red outlined area in Fig. 1), which provides intelligent resource allocation algorithms (such as the proposed price-based resource allocation schemes that are integrated into the CLEVER/EMPYREAN Service Orchestrator - SO) to optimally place the dynamic EUs’ workloads in the hyper-distributed computing continuum towards the overall system’s workload balancing and cost minimization, while also keeping EUs’ welfare (QoE) above certain thresholds. The SO receives telemetry data from the monitoring layer about the current system state, alarms, SLA conformance, etc. The monitoring layer also supports all the required ICT (Information and Telecommunication Technology) infrastructure and data exchange that is needed for the proposed pricing schemes (e.g. dynamic price signals, iterative messages between the SO and edge users, etc.). The onboarding layer ensures that the addition of every new device/EU is authenticated, traceable and protected against unauthorized access, thereby enhancing the overall system’s security and trustworthiness and enabling a robust resource orchestration process. Finally, the application layer ensures that all EUs’ preferences are effectively declared to the SO and that each EU’s resource provisioning requirements are satisfied by the SO. Finally, we assume that the EUs’ computing power is adequate in order to handle the required local calculations and communicate them efficiently to the SO.

Fig. 1 depicts a high-level operation of the proposed price-based EUA framework. We assume that the ESP serves many heterogeneous EUs. For example, EU1 is flexible; hence she is willing to get a worse QoE (i.e. get less resources) provided that she gets a considerable monetary reward. The ESP can exploit the aggregated flexibility from its EUs to minimize the cost for renting resources from the EIO. Thus, the proposed PSP scheme can flatten the aggregate demand curve incurring the following benefits: i) the system’s workload is dynamically balanced (both for the ESP and the EIO), ii) ESP’s cost for renting resources is minimized, iii) all EUs are satisfied with the fair resource allocation outcome.

3 Problem Formulation

In this section, we outline the prerequisites necessary for presenting our pricing schemes and introduce the widely accepted models (i.e. utility and cost functions) that serve as the testbed for evaluating and comparing SP and PSP.

Figure 1: System Architecture

We consider a decentralized market-based hyper-distributed computing ecosystem with a set of $N = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$ of n edge users (EUs), who use edge resources for their applications. It should be noted that the terms "flexible EU" and "flexible application" are used interchangeably and refer to the same notion. The resources that an edge user needs are heterogeneous, meaning that the computing resources of each EU may vary (e.g. CPU, memory, GPU). For simplicity, we set a resource bundle unit in the form of 1 VM as it is the current business norm of AmazonEC2, GoogleCloud and Microsoft Azure's spot VMs that contains :

$$\langle \text{CPU: 1 GB, GPU: 1 GB, RAM: 1 GB,} \\ \text{BW: 1 GBps, ROM: 10 GBs} \rangle$$

We consider a finite time horizon, which is divided into t time slots $T = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, t\}$ of equal duration. The needs of an EU's application i are denoted as x_i^t , where $i \in N$ and $t \in T$. The resources required by an EU's application i at time slot t are expressed by a utility function $u_i^t(x_i^t, \omega_i^t)$, where ω is an appropriate elasticity parameter. This utility function quantifies how much the EU i values the consumption x_i^t at time slot t . To better characterize the properties of the sigmoid utility function, the ICT literature draws on two concepts from microeconomics [12]. The first concept is that of diminishing returns, which, in our context, means that: i) the more an application consumes, the more utility it gains ($u_i^t(x_i^t, \omega_i^t)$ is increasing with x_i^t), ii) the more an application consumes, the less the added utility ($u_i^t(x_i^t, \omega_i^t)$ is concave, given the fact that an acceptable QoE level is achieved for every application).

The second concept relates to demand elasticity, defined as the rate of change of the utility function with respect to small changes in the consumption quantity. This is expressed through parameter ω_i^t , where low values of ω_i^t correspond to elastic demand (i.e., very responsive to price), whereas higher values correspond to inelastic demand (i.e., less responsive to price).

The dependence of ω_i^t on i and t captures the fact that different applications (or else EUs), at different time slots, have different needs.

We use the shorthand notation \dot{u}_i^t , where the dot outlines that it is a function. Given the concavity of \dot{u}_i^t , it is evident that a saturation point exists beyond which the utility no longer increases with x_i^t . This saturation point represents the application's maximum desired resources, denoted as \bar{x}_i^t . The maximum desired utility an application can achieve is represented as \bar{u}_i^t . In this study, we assume that the empirical utility function for each application is known to the ESP's Service Orchestrator (SO) component. This information can be obtained through machine learning models and profiling tools like [13], but this is out of this paper's scope. Therefore, without loss of generality, we adopt a concave function to represent the application's utility, as seen in other studies that utilize similar models (e.g. [3] [14]).

The supply side is usually modeled either as a game (e.g a market that admits to a Nash Equilibrium e.g.[8]) or as a cost function that approximately relates the aggregate demand with the costs of the resources supplied (e.g [3] and references therein). For this work, we assume that the system's costs denoted as C_N^t depend on the total load $\sum_{i \in N} x_i^t$ of the EUs' applications in the set N at time slot $t \in T$ through an increasing convex function. A quadratic cost function is commonly used in the international literature as a realistic approximation, which intuitively represents the penalization of resource contention or else the prioritization of resource allocation based on applications', edge users' requirements and performance objectives (or else the fact that the marginal resource price increases monotonically with resource utilization, to calculate prices for users in an online fashion). Hence, as resource contention increases, the cost associated with resource allocation increases quadratically to discourage over-utilization and mitigate congestion:

$$C_N^t = c \left(\sum_{i \in N} x_i^t \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

where c is a cost parameter. Eq. 1 represents the cost for the ESP to buy the resources that the system demands. The system needs to be budget balanced (i.e. the sum of EUs' payments are equal to the ESP's cost to hire the resources or else the system's cost). This quadratic function is widely used in social welfare maximization problems because it can capture non-linear cost behaviors representing increasing marginal costs.

The objective for each time slot $t \in T$ is to find the EU resource allocations $\hat{x}_i^t, \forall i \in N$ that maximize the system's efficiency (maximize the aggregate edge users' QoE and minimize the system's cost).

$$\max_{i \in N} \left\{ \sum_{i \in N} [u_i^t] - C_N^t \right\} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{i \in N} [p_i^t x_i^t] = C_N^t \quad (3)$$

Constraint (3) ensures that our system operates on a non-profit, budget-balanced basis. The model we propose focuses solely on real-time resource allocation, implying that the system does not rely on historical data. Consequently, the scheduling problem can be addressed for the time horizon T by independently solving for each timeslot. To solve Eq. (2), it is necessary for all EUs to reveal their QoE functions to the ESP and to permit the ESP to directly manage the resources they utilize. However, these conditions may not have a real market applicability. Therefore, the research community often explores interactive pricing mechanisms that reach an

equilibrium satisfying the desired KPIs. In light of Eq. (2), the prices established by the ESP aim at effectively allocating resource costs among EUs, inherently depending on C_N^t .

We consider selfish EUs that choose their x_i^t , to maximize their own welfare under the ESP's pricing:

$$x_i^t = \arg \max_{x_i^t} \{u_i^t - p^t x_i^t\} \quad (4)$$

Eq. (4) implies a price-taker EU, so Eq. (2) can be solved using dual decomposition method. In contrast, we examine scenarios where EUs are price-anticipating, meaning that they account for the impact of their x_i^t decisions on the price. hence, the EUA problem in Eq. (4) can be reformulated as follows:

$$x_i^t = \arg \max_{x_i^t} \{u_i^t - p^t(x_i^t, x_{-i}^t) x_i^t\} \quad (5)$$

In this context, the maximized expression represents the QoE. Additionally, the vector \mathbf{x}_{-i}^t denotes the resources consumed by applications other than application i . This interaction essentially forms the basis of a game Γ , where the players are EUs $i \in N$. In this game, an EU's strategy involves choosing x_i^t , and their payoff is determined by their welfare (QoE).

Furthermore, achieving efficient allocations generally necessitates that applications disclose their QoE functions to the SO. While this assumption simplifies the model for analytical purposes, it is quite strong and fails to adequately reflect the complexities of profiling applications [13]. Additionally, it raises concerns about privacy and accurate representation. Instead, we opt to remain agnostic regarding the specific form of the QoE function. Consequently, the efficiency of equilibria cannot be guaranteed in the general case. Despite this, our focus is on designing a pricing mechanism that ensures the following: i) the game Γ converges to a Nash Equilibrium (NE), and ii) the system at equilibrium achieves a desirable balance between efficiency, low cost and fairness.

4 Personalized Spot Pricing (PSP) algorithm

We start with the description of the baseline Spot Pricing (SP) approach being adopted by today's largest cloud service providers, too. For time slot $t \in H$, at the ESP-level, the applications' demands x_i^t are taken as input and the price p^t of time slot t (price per VM, which under SP is common for all EUs i) is calculated according to:

$$p^t = \frac{C_N^t}{\sum_{i \in N} x_i^t} \quad (6)$$

Eq. (6) leads to an EU's bill that is proportional to the application's resource demand ($\frac{x_i^t}{\sum_i x_i^t} C_N^t$). This ensures that the system is budget-balanced.

At the EU level, applications sequentially choose their x_i^t from Eq. (5). During this calculation, x_{-i}^t is considered fixed. Notice that although EU i might be agnostic of $p^t(x_i^t, x_{-i}^t)$, it can however detect the pricing trend by exchanging iterative messages with the ESP. More specifically, by trying different x_i^t and receiving the respective p^t , the EU can detect $p^t(x_i^t, x_{-i}^t)$ by applying some polynomial fitting algorithm. This approach allows for a distributed implementation in order to be scalable and resilient against to single points of failure.

After a limited number of sequential iterations (calculations) of each EU's updated x_i^t , the system converges to the equilibrium price, where noone wishes to further modify her x_i^t .

Each EU's final x_i^t at equilibrium is denoted as $x_i^{t,SP}$, $\forall i \in N$. The procedure is described in Algorithm 1 (where k denotes the algorithm's iterations).

Algorithm 1 Spot Pricing (SP)

- 1: **Initialization:**
 - 2: Set $k = 1$, $x_i^{t,k} = \bar{x}_i^t, \forall i \in N$ and $p^t = \frac{C_N^t}{\sum_{i \in N} x_i^t}$
 - 3: **repeat**
 - 4: **for** each $i \in N$ **do**
 - 5: Calculate p^t from (6)
 - 6: Calculate $x_i^{t,k+1}$ by solving (5)
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: Calculate divergence $\Delta = \max(|x_i^{t,k+1} - x_i^{t,k}|)$
 - 9: Set $k = k + 1$
 - 10: **until** $\Delta < \epsilon$ (desired accuracy)
-

We now introduce the concept of the proposed Personalized Spot Pricing (PSP) algorithm, where the price is no longer a uniform scalar p^t (i.e. the same for all EUs $i \in N$), but rather each EU receives an individual price p_i^t .

From the range of possible PSP mechanisms, we develop a specific method designed to excel in the KPIs mentioned in section I. The proposed mechanism assigns lower prices to EUs (apps) who consume a smaller percentage of their desired resources (\bar{x}_i^t), and higher prices to those who consume a larger percentage of their desired resources. More specifically, for an application i and a time slot t , the price p_i^t is allocated based on the extent to which the EU's application reduces the resources it needs to operate. EUs with more elastic demand receive lower prices, while those with less elastic demand receive higher prices. It is important to note that PSP assumes knowledge of the resources needed (\bar{x}_i^t). If an EU is allowed to declare an inflated desired consumption, PSP would favor it. Therefore, PSP is suitable for automated environments (via ICT systems) such as an application that declares the resources which are needed in order to run. Truthfulness property is out of this paper's scope and will be confronted as a future work as well as the possibility of EUs to form dynamic resource associations that may operate competitively/cooperatively (cf. our ongoing work in [7]) in order to gain more market power.

In order to achieve prices with a discount (or else reward) proportional to the percentage of workload curtailments, we set:

$$(p_i^t - \tilde{p}^t)/\tilde{p}^t = (x_i^t - \bar{x}_i^t)/\bar{x}_i^t \quad (7)$$

where \tilde{p}^t is introduced in order to tune the prices, so that constraint (3) holds. Let us denote as β_i^t the percentage of the curtailment of EU i at time instant t :

$$\beta_i^t = (x_i^t - \bar{x}_i^t)/\bar{x}_i^t \quad (8)$$

Thus, Eq. (7) through the use of (8) becomes:

$$p_i^t = \tilde{p}^t(1 + \beta_i^t) \quad (9)$$

Now, through the use of (3) we have:

$$\tilde{p}^t = \frac{C_N^t}{\sum_{i \in N} x_i^t(1 + \beta_i^t)} \quad (10)$$

If we now combine (9) and (10), we have:

$$p_i^t = (1 + \beta_i^t) \frac{C_N^t}{\sum_{i \in N} x_i^t (1 + \beta_i^t)} \quad (11)$$

In the proposed mechanism, we iteratively solve (5) and calculate the prices from (11).

Algorithm 2 Personalized Spot Pricing (PSP)

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1: Initialization:
2: Set  $k = 1$ ,  $x_i^{t,k} = \bar{x}_i^t, \forall i \in N$ 
3: repeat
4:   for each  $i \in N$  do
5:     repeat
6:       Calculate  $p^t$  from (11)
7:       Calculate  $x_i^{t,k+1}$  by solving (5)
8:     until convergence
9:   end for
10:  Calculate divergence  $\Delta = \max(|x_i^{t,k+1} - x_i^{t,k}|)$ 
11:  Set  $k = k + 1$ 
12: until  $\Delta < \epsilon$  (desired accuracy)

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5 Performance Evaluation Results

In this section, we present the simulation results evaluating the performance of the proposed PSP mechanism against the KPIs of interest. The SP mechanism is employed as a benchmark for comparative analysis. The evaluation encompasses a range of scenarios based on different assumptions regarding the parameter values in both models.

In order to evaluate pricing mechanisms, the research community (e.g. [3] [14] and references therein) models end users' utility as a concave and increasing function of x_i^t and ω_i^t with a constant maximum value after a saturation point:

$$u_i^t(x_i^t, \omega_i) = \begin{cases} \bar{u}_i^t - \omega_i^t (x_i^t - \bar{x}_i^t)^2 & 0 < x_i^t < \bar{x}_i^t \\ \bar{u}_i^t & x_i^t \geq \bar{x}_i^t \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

We present simulation results for a representative sample of 40 users. We split the 40 users into two clusters of 20 users each; the flexible (where the needs for VMs follow the normal distribution with mean $\mu_0 = 10$ and standard deviation $\sigma_0 = 1.5$) and the inflexible (where the needs follow a uniform distribution $U(a, b)$ with parameters $a = 0$ and $b = 20$, which gives a mean value of 10). User's maximum utility (i.e., utility at $x_i^t \geq \bar{x}_i^t$) was set to $\bar{u}_i^t = \omega_i^t (\bar{x}_i^t)^2$ and the epsilon parameter is set to $\epsilon = 0.01$, parameter c was set to $c = 0.02$. The flexibility parameter ω_i^t for each user i was selected randomly in the interval $[0.1, 5]$. Finally, since the optimization problem can be addressed independently, we conduct the simulation for a single time slot without any loss of generality.

The concept of user elasticity, as illustrated in Figure 2, presents an actual model of user elasticity, depicting the relationship between resource allocation and user's utility - Quality of Experience (QoE) as a function of elasticity parameter ω . The plot shows three curves corresponding to different elasticity values of $\omega = [1, 2, 3]$. The horizontal axis, denoted as \mathbf{x} ,

Figure 2: User's elasticities based on the ω

represents the resources, with a critical value marked as \bar{x} . The vertical axis measures the utility, with the maximum utility level U_{max} indicated.

As the elasticity parameter increases, users exhibit greater flexibility in their ability to adapt to the different available resources. The blue curve, representing the $\omega = 3$, reflects an elastic user, where utility increases gradually as resources approach the desired, but also starting with high utility, in contrast with the green curve and the inelastic user with $\omega = 1$ whose utility rises the same way the resources level rise, indicating a lower tolerance for deviation from ideal resource allocation before the maximum utility is reached.

In this context, higher ω values correspond to more flexible and adaptive users, achieving their maximum utility with less sensitivity to the given amount of resources. On the other hand, lower ω values indicate users with lower elasticity, who require more precise resource allocation to achieve maximum utility.

In correspondence with the three previously presented KPIs, we define four index metrics for the evaluation:

1. AEUW is an index for the system's efficiency (cf. KPI 1).

$$AEUW = \sum_{i \in N} (u_i^t - p_i^t x_i^t) \quad (13)$$

2. The allocation's cost C is also a straightforward index metric of the system's cost (cf. KPI 2).

$$C = c \left(\sum_{i \in N} [x_i^t] \right)^2 \quad (14)$$

We assess the performance of the PSP and SP mechanisms concerning the previously defined KPIs, varying the values of c and ω_i^t . This evaluation aims to demonstrate that the efficacy of our pricing mechanism remains robust irrespective of the system's parameters. It is important to note that these KPIs 1 and 2 are generally conflicting. For instance, minimizing the system's cost might result in reduced users' welfare due to decreased consumption, unless EUs are incentivized with lower prices to offset the impact on their welfare.

3. Fairness (F_i) indicates the fraction of user's i contribution to system cost reduction that she will be rewarded in terms of bill discount (cf. KPI 3).

$$FR_i = \frac{D_i^A}{D_i^R} \quad \forall i \in N \quad (15)$$

where

$$D_i^A = \frac{C \left(\sum_{i=1}^N x_i^t \right) (x_i^t - \bar{x}_i^t) - C \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \bar{x}_i^t \right)}{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i^t - \sum_{i=1}^N \bar{x}_i^t} \quad (16)$$

represents the discount achieved by EU i , i.e., her contribution to the system cost reduction, as a fraction of the summation of all EUs' corresponding contributions.

$$D_i^R = x_i^t \frac{C \left(\sum_{i=1}^N x_i^t \right)}{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i^t} - x_i^t p_i^t \quad (17)$$

represents the discount that EU i receives in her bill as a portion of the total discount in all EUs' bills.

4. End-User Welfare Deviation (EUWD) is defined to capture the degree of the deviation of EU i from the average user's welfare:

$$UWD_i = \frac{[(u_i^t - p_i^t x_i^t) - \frac{AEUW}{n}]}{\frac{AEUW}{n}} \quad \forall i \in N \quad (18)$$

In all the figures below, we normalized each metric (KPI) by dividing with the highest metric value.

In figure 3, we present a comparison of system costs (C) under the proposed PSP and baseline SP schemes as a function of the elasticity parameter ω . The results indicate that the PSP mechanism consistently achieves a reduction in system costs, demonstrating significant and reliable performance improvements across various values of the elasticity parameter for the participating EUs. In fact, the PSP scheme achieves approximately 15% system costs' reduction in low elasticity scenarios, while this reduction is 35% in high elasticity scenarios. Indeed, the

Figure 3: System costs of PSP and SP as a function of ω

proposed PSP scheme leads to smaller aggregate consumption by the EUs, so the system’s cost is decreased, too. As expected, the difference between PSP and SP is very small when most of the EUs are not elastic at all.

The reason behind the reduction of system costs is clarified via Fig 4, where we present the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the FR_i metric exhibited by the users i in N . The dotted vertical lines represent the average EUWD of all users. As depicted in figure 4, under PSP, edge users obtain benefits, according to their behavioral change. In more detail, we observe that PSP not only offers a better trade-off between AEUW and C (the average Fairness for PSP is closer to 1 than the average Fairness for SP), but also results in a much narrower distribution of users around the average. This means that the behavioral change that the EUs offer is better and more fairly reciprocated. In other words, with the proposed PSP, inelastic users do not benefit from the actions of elastic EUs. Figure 5 validates that the reduction in the system’s cost is achieved by negligibly sacrificing the AEUW up to 2.5%. This is intuitively explained by the fact that PSP allocates monetary savings to the elastic EUs that mostly contribute to the system’s cost reduction and not to the inelastic ones.

6 Conclusions and Future Work

We considered a business model of a budget-balanced aggregating entity serving as Edge Service Provider (ESP) for its registered users. Our proposed personalized spot pricing scheme models multiple types of elastic edge users, striking an optimal trade-off between aggregate edge users’ welfare, system’s cost and fair allocation of rewards to all edge users according to each one’s

Figure 4: CDF of Fairness (F_i) among participating users under PSP and SP pricing.

Figure 5: AEUW under PSP and SP as a function of cost parameter c

contribution to the system’s cost reduction. Our future research includes the modelling of various types of flexible workloads (e.g. distributed ML applications which exhibit high flexibility

with respect to performance, distributed batch processing applications which exhibit high temporal/spatial flexibility, etc.), multi-period scheduling of workloads and regulatory aspects of an edge computing market, where multiple ESPs may compete with each other (i.e. market equilibrium analysis) and/or collaborate under an edge federation market architecture.

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